

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MANAGEMENT BEHAVIOR OF ORGANIZATIONAL PERSONNEL

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Abstract: *In the context of the digital transformation of all spheres of human life, more and more problems are manifested with insufficient adaptability to changes, uncontrolled reactions due to a large array of digital sources of information and digital risks (cyber-attacks, digital fraud) and panics arising against this background. Panic is a condition that occurs under conditions of stress and danger, when people lose control of their behavior due to overwhelm with emotions. In this article, we will consider panic as a socio-psychological phenomenon, discuss the social conditions that contribute to its occurrence in large social groups, as well as groups of people according to their behavior in conditions of panic and factors predisposing to the occurrence of panic states.*

Keywords: *Digital technologies, management, behavior, panic, organizational personnel, person*

Аннотация: *В условиях цифровой трансформации всех сфер жизнедеятельности человека все больше проблем проявляется с недостаточной его адаптивностью к изменениям, неконтролируемыми реакциями в связи с большим массивом цифровых источников информации и цифровых рисков (кибератак, цифрового мошенничества) и возникающих на этом фоне паник. Паника — это состояние, возникающее в условиях стресса и опасности, когда люди теряют контроль над своим поведением из-за переполненности эмоциями. В этой статье рассмотрим панику как социально-психологическое явление, обсудим социальные условия, способствующие её возникновению в больших социальных группах, а также группы людей по их поведению в условиях паники и факторы, предрасполагающие к возникновению панических состояний.*

Ключевые слова: *Цифровые технологии, управление, поведение, паника, персонал организации, человек*

Introduction. Let us substantiate the role of digital technologies in managing the behavior of organizational personnel in order to understand the mechanisms of preventing panic and countering the provocation of panic states [1]. Let us identify and characterize the social conditions that contribute to panic in large social groups. In order to understand what social conditions, contribute to the emergence of panic in large social groups, it is important to consider the main factors influencing the occurrence of such a phenomenon from the perspective of an interdisciplinary approach.

Research methods. From the standpoint of medical science, panic can be characterized by the term “stress” “... a set of nonspecific adaptive (normal) reactions of the body to the influence of various unfavorable physical or psychological stress factors that disrupt its homeostasis, as well as the corresponding state of the nervous system of the body (or the body as a whole)”. [2]

The World Health Organization defines stress “...as a state of anxiety or mental tension caused by a difficult situation. Stress is a natural human reaction that focuses attention on problems or threats that arise in everyday life.” [3]

In the field of civil defense, emergency situations and disaster management, three approaches have been adopted to defining danger as: the possibility of “... causing harm, property (material), physical or moral (spiritual) damage to the individual, society, state...” [4]; threat, the likelihood of “...the occurrence of a potentially destructive phenomenon in a given period of time and in a certain area...” [4]; “...a process, property or state of nature, society or technology that poses a threat to the life, health or well-being of people, economic objects or the environment...”. [4]

In modern conditions of mass access to information and sources of obtaining it, however, there is an acute problem of “... the lack of necessary information, and not information in general... In the huge information flow, people cannot find knowledge that would contribute to their development. A huge amount of media literally persecutes people, preventing them from receiving important and necessary information...” [5], distorting people’s ideas about any events or personalities, exaggerated or on the contrary, with a decrease in relevance and relevant data, thereby creating the preconditions for panic.

In modern society, on the threshold of the transition to a new stage of development of high technologies, Industry 5.0, a paradoxical phenomenon has become the mass infantilization of society and individuals. In psychology, infantilization is “... a process in which society loses its maturity, independence, responsibility and ability to develop...” caused by “political, economic, cultural, informational, etc.” [6]; factors, and the information factor, and specifically the development of the Internet and social networks, is dominant in the infantilization of society, since “... people spend more and more time in the virtual world, where it is easy for them to escape reality and responsibility. They create their own virtual images, prefer computer games and media content that justifies and supports their infantile behavior...”. [6]

The change in social values in modern society is manifested in the fact that priority is given to individual well-being, comfort and instant satisfaction of needs. People tend to shift “...responsibility for their actions and problems...to others, and individuals become increasingly self-oriented and think little about things.” [6] The move into virtual reality and offline formats of interaction in all spheres of social relations also contributes to the perversion of social norms and culture. Avoidance of personal, personal responsibility is manifested in the fact that responsibility is shifted not so much to some specific individuals, but to magical circumstances that have developed or are predetermined by fate. The negative “...role of magical thinking and

modern trends...” [6] is manifested in the fact that “... young people prefer to believe in promises of instant success and easy solutions instead of investing effort in their development and achieving their goals... ” [6]

This becomes a big problem for managing human behavior in general and, in particular, the labor behavior of organizational personnel. In various panic situations, people often exhibit different types of behavior, which can be classified as follows:

1. Leaders are people who take responsibility for others, try to control the situation and direct the behavior of others. Their decisions can either calm or stimulate panic in the group, depending on the adequacy of their actions.

2. Imitators - in a group there are always people who are inclined to imitate the behavior of others. Their response to panic depends on how the leaders behave. By supporting the leader, they can help calm panic.

3. Passive observers are people who are not active, often due to stress or numbness. Their behavior can be counterproductive because they usually do nothing to calm panic.

4. Aggressive Individuals – In stressful situations, some people may become aggressive due to loss of control. They can create additional problems in an already difficult situation, increasing tension in the group [7].

Results. In conclusion, we note that the management of modern organizations, to a greater extent than ever, must have the competence to manage staff behavior in order to prevent panic, identify and neutralize the negative impact of factors that may predispose people to panic:

- individual characteristics: some people have a higher predisposition to panic due to their character, biological characteristics or previously suffered traumatic situations;

- social environment: parental model, media, education and other aspects of the social environment can form people's behavioral stereotypes in stressful situations, including panic reactions;

- lack of training and practice: people who rarely find themselves in stressful situations, or who have no experience in managing stress, may be less prepared to manage their emotions and behavior in critical situations [8].

Understanding these conditions, types of behavior and predisposing factors helps us more deeply understand the essence of panic as a socio-psychological phenomenon. Taking these aspects into account, more effective strategies for preventing and managing panic conditions in society can be developed.

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